

PREMIERE Rubric for the Multi-actor Approach, version 2. June 2026.
 (This is a self-descriptive rubric for Multi-actor proposal preparation and for evaluation.
 See Section 6 on PREMIERE Discussion Paper no.1 for further details).

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Note: Following PREMIERE glossary here we define **actor** as 'a partner taking part in project activities and contributing to project outcomes', and a **stakeholder** as 'people or organisations that will benefit from, be impacted by, or have a legitimate interest (or stake) in the project at some point in time; they are not required to be active in the project's co-creation'. The nine criteria on this rubric encompass the seven requirements of the Multi-actor approach.

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CRITERIA TO BE CONSIDERED WHEN WRITING / EVALUATING MULTI-ACTOR APPROACH PROPOSALS					
Criteria	Exemplary / 5	Great / 4	Good / 2	Routine / 1	Insufficient/0
	Best of best means:	Best means:	Correct means:	Minimum means:	Below threshold
1 Objectives and planning of the proposal target needs / problems / challenges of, and opportunities for, the (end-)users of the project results	<p>Takes a large-scale approach to complex challenges / opportunities at multi-actor level.</p> <p>Clearly shows a co-creative ongoing analysis (started at proposal preparation stage or before) with users involved, to solve multiple challenges simultaneously.</p>	<p>Addresses a significant need of high multi-actor value.</p> <p>A co-creative process of connection between objectives and planning of the proposal and the users of the project is presented specifying the needs, problems, challenges and opportunities, and how these will be jointly co-created to deliver a successful solution.</p>	<p>The focus of the proposal is partial, marginal or has limitations on its multi-actor value.</p> <p>There is a clear connection between objectives and planning of the proposal and the users of the project results specifying the needs, problems, challenges and opportunities addressed toward a solution or partial solution.</p>	<p>The focus of the proposal is unclear or it responds to an interest of a limited group of actors.</p> <p>Needs / problems / challenges of and opportunities for the (end-)users of the project results are partially or briefly addressed creating limited and or decontextualized knowledge.</p>	<p>There is no focus for the proposal or it is clearly not well formulated.</p> <p>Needs / problems / challenges of and opportunities for the (end-)users of the project results are insufficiently or incorrectly addressed in the objectives and planning of the proposal</p>
2 Key actors are well identified in the proposal, including interactive innovation groups, such as EIP-AGRI Operational Groups.	<p>The proposal includes a very well-balanced, well developed and clearly described composition of actors, and all partners have a clearly delineated and valid role in the project.</p> <p>It encompasses a wide range of actors, balanced at geographical as well as social, gender, sectoral and at 4-helix levels. Interactive innovation groups in the AKIS ecosystem and beyond, including OG where relevant, have a structural role in the actors framework of the proposal.</p>	<p>The proposal includes a thorough and well argued selection of actors to be involved at different levels. All key groups are represented, with consideration to geographical balance, and including interactive innovation groups in the AKIS ecosystem.</p>	<p>The proposal identifies and includes major actor types but not a detailed and well argued selection of actors to be involved at different levels. Key groups, geographical balance and interactive innovation groups in the AKIS ecosystem are discussed, but it is unclear if the proposal covers them adequately.</p>	<p>The proposal outlines a number of actors with limited reasoning for the selection.-Key groups not identified in detail, making it difficult to value their representativeness. No consideration to geographical balance or to any other criteria, interactive innovation groups in the AKIS ecosystem not considered or poorly analysed.</p>	<p>Insufficient detail provided on the number and type of actors.</p>

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<p>There is a genuine and sufficient involvement of targeted actors and stakeholders, ensured and demonstrated over the whole course of the project.</p>	<p><i>The proposal openly and actively seeks ongoing critical input, feedback, and feed-forward from a range of stakeholders, including embedded bottom-up and top-down initiatives. Harder-to-reach and specific knowledge groups are part of the consortium in well-defined roles. Encouraging and rewarding transformative mutual learning. Employing an evolving integrative method and consciously employing a transdisciplinary process .</i></p>	<p><i>Inviting, incorporating and integrating stakeholder views at various points along the research and innovation process. Harder-to-reach and specific knowledge groups are well identified and partly engaged in the proposal. Actively seeking dialogic interaction with stakeholders and open to mutual learning. Encompassing a wide range of methods (including, but not only, co-creation, co-implementation, co-evaluation) and adopting an interdisciplinary process.</i></p>	<p><i>Limited stages of the research and innovation process open for stakeholder engagement. Tendency toward one-way forms of communication (e.g. validation only) with stakeholders but open to some interaction. Involving some level of methodological diversity and multidisciplinary practice. Hard to reach and specific knowledge groups somewhat considered.</i></p>	<p>Limited involvement (or insufficient evidence of) of targeted actors in the research and innovation process which may be one-way and with limited methodological and disciplinary diversity. Lack of a comprehensive bottom-up approach with targeted actors.</p>	<p>Concept and methodology do poorly show how practitioners and their organisations are targeted from the planning to the execution of the project work.</p>
<p>Research and innovation process open to dialogue and responsive to actors and stakeholders</p>	<p><i>Structured, purposeful periodic analytical review of underlying values, assumptions and choices. Actively seeking critical feedback from a wide group of sources and actors, including networking structures among dispersed communities. Evidence of potential to adapt at a range of points in response to in-train reflective practice and external review/input/feedback. Active use of complementary forms of knowledge, practitioners practical and local knowledge and/or entrepreneurial skills to develop solutions.</i></p>	<p><i>Occasional use of structured process for reflecting on underlying values, assumptions and choices. Actively seeking critical feedback from select sources and actors. Clear indications of a capacity to adapt in response to reflective practice and external feedback. Proposal shows signs of some capacity to use practice and local knowledge from practitioners.</i></p>	<p><i>Informal, one-off or ad hoc process for considering underlying values, assumptions and choices of stakeholders. Accepting critical feedback when offered. Stated willingness to accept change in response to internal reflective practice or external review and critique.</i></p>	<p><i>No process for facilitating reflective practice. No critique sought. No evidence for potential for change in response to criticism / unsolicited feedback.</i></p>	<p>Practitioners and (end) users mainly involved as a study-object. Dialogue mostly one-way.</p>

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<p>5</p> <p>Building blocks for the project proposal clearly come from science as well as from practice and tacit knowledge: it is a 'co-creation' process</p>	<p>The project proposal is co-designed between all actors involved and deeply fundamented in a co-creative work process clearly blending science and practice knowledge/techniques in a shared learning by-doing process. Creation of 'co-ownership' of results for (end-) users and practitioners is high-quality and its feasibility is clearly demonstrated via knowledge exchange activities, and balanced decision making procedures.</p>	<p>The project proposal is based on some dialogue and contribution by actors involved and shows means and strategies for co-creative work process that shall ensure science and practice collaboration. Bottom-up and top-down initiatives are considered. Knowledge exchange activities are planned at a scale which should facilitate 'co-ownership' of results for (end-) users and practitioners.</p>	<p>The project proposal plans to carry out occasional actions promoting dialogue and contribution towards co-creation by actors involved, without a consistent and continued strategy for science and practice collaboration throughout the project. Bottom-up and top-down initiatives are considered but not clearly aligned to ensure science-practice exchange.</p>	<p>The proposal has a classical research for practice transfer approach. Co-creative science-practice is largely absent or, if mentioned, it follows a non-co-creative approach. Little to no use of practitioner and traditional knowledge.</p>	<p>The co-creation principle is not adequately addressed. Knowledge exchange and cross-fertilisation of skills is not demonstrated</p>
<p>6</p> <p>Project results are ready for practice and broadly implemented</p>	<p>Ensure wide dissemination of results at practice and external level, by actively overcoming language and geographical barriers, and actively using synergies between projects at European scale, communities of practice and easy to access outputs in general. Project results planned for use beyond the project duration.</p>	<p>Clear dissemination of results at the practice and external levels, with some identified limitations with contingency plans. Active plans to make broad use of exchange opportunities with farmers, visitors and at trainings. Project results planned for use beyond the project duration.</p>	<p>Dissemination of results at practice and external level considered in general terms with no clear means to reach out practitioners. Limited plans to make use of exchange opportunities with farmers, visitors and at trainings. General but limited plans to use results beyond the project duration.</p>	<p>Basic and classical means of dissemination of results at practice and external level, correction measures not identified. Target groups identified without a clear outreach strategy. Use of project results beyond the project duration with little credibility.</p>	<p>Project results dissemination limited to the project digital media or collateral activities planned by some partners. Practice level not specifically addressed. Specific target groups not identified.</p>
<p>7</p> <p>The project facilitates the multi-actor engagement process by making use of the most appropriate methods and expertise</p>	<p>MAA is framed in innovative directions beyond current practice, with new ideas being pursued through appropriate methods. Resources are carefully considered and allocated to efficiently achieve maximum use and impact of the MAA, with all partners engaged. Stakeholder engagement consideration is given to preconditions, process and products.</p>	<p>New methods for MAA are being developed according to new ideas within an established problem framing. The use of resources is explicitly justified in relation to the MAA. Stakeholder engagement consideration is given to process and products.</p>	<p>New ideas are being pursued through established MAA methods within an accepted problem framing. Resources are too limited, or inefficiently employed in relation to MAA. Stakeholder engagement consideration is given to envisaged products.</p>	<p>Problem framing, ideas and methods fall within established paradigms of the MAA. Extensive resources (e.g. time, money, personnel, etc.) are dedicated to work with minimal significance or potential impact on MAA. No consideration is given to the stakeholder engagement of operating preconditions, research and innovation process or envisaged products</p>	<p>Methods are very general, basically with unidirectional participation in MAA. No resources are planned for MAA. The project preconditions, process and products are totally disconnected of the stakeholders it targets.</p>

<p>8</p> <p>The project provides an appropriate number of 'practice abstracts' in the common EIP-AGRI format, or other similarly effective solutions for topics outside EIP-AGRI / CAP specific objectives.</p>	<p>Innovative practice abstracts are planned, and quantified in number and expected dissemination. Different abstract dissemination tools, events and activities are identified, including open source databases targeting different stakeholder types like Zenodo, CAP network, or FarmBook. Practice abstracts have been developed within a MAA. Content of the practice abstracts has been pre-tested for practitioners usability and it is clear and visual.</p>	<p>Practice abstracts are clearly described and consider means of dissemination. MAA is part of the abstracts development. Content of the practice abstracts is designed for clarity and visual use.</p>	<p>Practice abstracts are described in some detail and are part of the general project dissemination plans. No further concretion is provided.</p>	<p>The proposal mentions practice abstracts without further detail on their development and dissemination.</p>	<p>The proposal misses to mention practice abstracts.</p>
<p>9</p> <p>MAA is embedded throughout the Horizon proposal in all 3 sections (Excellence, Impact, Implementation)</p>	<p>Multi-actor approach is transversal in the project proposal and it is clearly highlighted in all 3 sections and in those sections and aspects of the proposal where it is relevant. Partner descriptions in Part A address their MAA role as well. Proposal budget is according to its MAA.</p>	<p>Multi-actor approach is evident throughout the project proposal and all 3 sections make reference to it.</p>	<p>MAA is well described in Excellence section, and mentioned in a few other points of the proposal.</p>	<p>MAA is part of the proposal but only Implementation makes it explicit.</p>	<p>MAA is only implicit in Excellence or Implementation, without a clear development in the proposal.</p>

<p>Changes from previous versions</p>					
<p>Version 2, 16.6.2026</p>					
<p>-The three specific criteria for ESR writing have been eliminated (available in the discussion paper).</p>					
<p>-All texts have been revised with very minor corrections. In criteria 1 and 5 redundant text has been eliminated</p>					
<p>Cited reference</p>					
<p>PREMIERE Discussion Paper no.1: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8377183</p>					